

Action of Hydrazides. Part IV. Condensation of Diarylaminoguanidines with Phenanthraquinone and some of its Derivatives.

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Thiele and Behan (*Annalen*, 1898, 302, 303) have shown that osazones are formed in the reaction between aminoguanidine and aliphatic-1:2-diketones whilst benzil gives 8-amino-5:6-diphenyl-1:2:4-triazine; and it has also been shown (De, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 183) that aminoguanidine reacts with most of the aromatic 1:2-diketones to yield triazines. Here the tendency to form ring compounds with the simultaneous elimination of two molecules of water has been attributed to the greater basicity of aminoguanidine which contains an amino-group in addition to a hydrazine residue.

In the present paper diphenylaminoguanidine, di-*p*-tolylaminoguanidine and di- β -naphthylaminoguanidine have been condensed with phenanthraquinone, its 2-nitro- and 2:7-dinitro-substitution products. The object of the present communication is to see what happens if the basicity of the amino-group in $\text{--C}(\text{:NH})\text{NH}_2$ of aminoguanidine is diminished by taking the aryl substitution products mentioned before. It should be observed here that by taking the aryl substitution products of aminoguanidine, the formation of a triazine ring by immediate elimination of water from the diarylaminoguanidinephenanthraquinone (I) is prevented, and consequently the first product of the reaction will have a hydrazone structure. When the monoxime of phenanthraquinone or its substitution products are condensed with the various diarylaminoguanidines in alcoholic solution the hydrazone-oximes are formed in good yield by the elimination of a molecule of water. When the same reactions are allowed to take place in glacial acetic acid solution or when the hydrazone-oximes are heated with glacial acetic acid, different compounds are formed.

As has been shown (De, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 373) that when phenanthraquinonemoxime and carbonylhydrazide (or thiocarbonylhydrazide) are allowed to react, the product obtained is a bistriazole derivative, so it might be expected by analogy that the compound derived from phenanthraquinonemoxime and diphenyl aminoguanidine *e.g.*, should have a similar triazole structure (III) or the product might be a triazine derivative (IV).

A triazine ring somewhat different from the one suggested above can also be supposed to be formed in which the elimination of a molecule of hydroxylamine is to be presumed. To account for this the migration of a hydrogen atom must first be assumed forming an intermediate azo-compound (V) which will then part with a molecule of phenylhydroxylamine to form the triazine (VI). The mechanism of the reaction can be illustrated, thus:

But the compound actually isolated is neither (III) nor (IV) or (VI). From the analytical results it appears that the compound from phenanthraquinonemoxime and diphenylaminoguanidine, for example, possesses an empirical formula, $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2$. The only possible way in which the formation of such a compound can be explained is that the moment the azo-compound is formed it undergoes fission at the azo-linking with the liberation of two atoms of nitrogen and the carbon atoms become linked together with the formation of an unstable compound which then parts with a molecule of hydroxylamine to form a ring (VII). The various changes can be explained by means of the following scheme:

The migration of a hydrogen atom in diarylamino-guanidine phenanthraquinonemonoxime to facilitate the formation of a four-membered ring, at once suggested itself whether it was possible to obtain ring-compounds from the various diarylamino-guanidine-phenanthraquinones. In all these cases if the reaction proceeds normally two compounds may, possibly be formed from each of these compounds, namely, one by the elimination of a molecule of water and the other by the loss of phenylhydroxylamine. The reaction can be explained by taking, for example, diphenylamino-guanidinephenanthraquinone (VIII) which is first transformed into an intermediate azo-compound (IX) from which there results either 3-phenylimino-4-phenyl-1:2:4-phenanthrotriazine (X) or anilino-phenanthrotriazole (XI).

But the compound actually isolated is quite different from (X) or (XI) as it contains a very low percentage of nitrogen than what is demanded by the compound (X) or (XI). The analytical results show that this compound should be derived from compound (XI) with two atoms of nitrogen less. The only possible way to explain the formation of such a compound is that the azo-compound (IX) momentarily formed, simultaneously parts with the group $\cdot\text{N}=\text{N}\cdot$ and a molecule of phenylhydroxylamine and an unstable compound (XII) is formed with the carbon valencies free, this then uniting to form the compound (XIII), thus:

Although the elimination of nitrogen from compounds of this type is not to be found in literature and appears to be the first of its kind yet such a phenomenon in ring-compounds is not altogether new (Buchner and Curtius, *Ber.*, 1865, 18, 297; Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2950; Schlotterbeck, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 479; etc.). It should be marked here that in all the cyclic compounds from which nitrogen is known to be eliminated, the two nitrogen atoms are linked together by a double bond; and it appears to the present authors that in all the cases examined such a linkage between the nitrogen atoms is probably formed by the migration of a hydrogen atom as postulated, and compounds of the types (VI and XI) are actually produced which, being unstable under the experimental condition, part with nitrogen. Similar reactions have been observed in other cases which will shortly be communicated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Phenanthraquinone diphenylaminoguanidine.—In an alcoholic solution of phenanthraquinone and diphenylaminoguanidine, there was a sudden change of colour from yellow to orange-yellow with the separation of a yellow crystalline product which was recrystallised from pyridine in deep yellow needles, m.p. 240°. (Found: N, 13.29. $C_{27}H_{20}ON_4$ requires N, 13.46 per cent.).

The above compound was heated in presence of acetic acid for 5 to 6 hours when the colour changed from yellow to orange and finally to green. The solution was filtered from the substance which was successively boiled with acetic acid and pyridine and crystallised from nitrobenzene in green plates, m. p. above 300°. (Found: C, 90.55; H, 4.84; N, 4.80. $C_{21}H_{13}N$ requires C, 90.92; H, 4.66; N, 5.02 per cent.).

Phenanthraquinonemonozime diphenylaminoguanidine was obtained from alcohol as a yellow mass which was crystallised from acetic acid in deep yellow needles, m.p. 155°. (Found: N, 16.59. $C_{27}H_{21}ON_5$ requires N, 16.24 per cent.).

N.B.—That nitrogen is actually evolved has been proved experimentally by collecting the gas (air being first of all driven off) in a nitrometer over caustic potash and driving off the evolved nitrogen from the reaction flask by means of carbon dioxide.

The above compound was heated in acetic acid solution for 4 to 5 hours. The solid so obtained was crystallised from alcohol in yellow rectangles, m.p. 180° (decomp.). (Found: C, 87·76; H, 4·99; N, 7·70. $C_{27}H_{18}N_2$ requires C, 87·55; H, 4·86; N, 7·55 per cent.).

2-Nitrophenanthraquinonediphenylaminoguanidine—From an alcoholic solution of diphenylaminoguanidine and 2-nitrophenanthraquinone separated a red product which was crystallised from pyridine in red rectangles, m.p. 238°. (Found: N, 15·37. $C_{27}H_{10}O_3N_5$ requires N, 15·18 per cent.).

The above substance when heated for 5 to 6 hours with acetic acid gradually went into solution and then a solid product separated. This was successively boiled with acetic acid and pyridine and the residue crystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. above 300°. (Found: C, 77·98; H, 3·86; N, 8·79. $C_{21}H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires C, 77·77; H, 3·74; N, 8·64 per cent.).

2-Nitrophenanthraquinonemonoxime diphenylaminoguanidine—, separated from alcohol and was crystallised from a mixture of water and pyridine in red needles, m.p. 233°. (Found: N, 18·02. $C_{27}H_{20}O_3N_6$ requires N, 17·65 per cent.).

The above substance was heated with acetic acid for 5 to 6 hours and the solid that separated was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 193°. (Found: C, 78·30; H, 4·24; N, 10·24. $C_{27}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires C, 78·07; H, 4·09; N, 10·12 per cent.).

2:7-Dinitrophenanthraquinone diphenylaminoguanidine separated from alcohol as a dark coloured solid which was crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and water in violet rectangles, m.p. 235°. (Found: N, 16·84. $C_{27}H_{18}O_5N_6$ requires N, 16·60 per cent.).

The above substance was heated with acetic acid for 5 to 6 hours when the violet colour of the solid was gradually changed to green. This was then boiled with pyridine and acetic acid and the residue was crystallised from nitrobenzene as a green crystalline power, m.p. above 300°. (Found: C, 68·54; H, 3·13; N, 11·48. $C_{21}H_{11}O_4N_3$ requires C, 68·29; H, 2·99; N, 11·88 per cent.).

2:7-Dinitrophenanthraquinonemonoxime diphenylaminoguanidine obtained from the components in alcoholic solution when the colour of the monoxime gradually changed to green. This was crystallised from pyridine and water. The colour changes to brown at 230° and melts at 245°. (Found: N, 18·98. $C_{27}H_{10}O_5N_7$ requires N, 18·81 per cent.).

The above substance was heated with glacial acetic acid for 2 to 3 hours. The solid was crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and water, m.p. 202°. (Found: N, 12·66. $C_{27}H_{16}O_4N_4$ requires N, 12·18 per cent.).

Phenanthraquinone di-p-tolylaminoguanidine, obtained from the components and alcohol as a red solid mass was crystallised from pyridine in red rectangles, m.p. 236°. (Found: N, 12·75. $C_{29}H_{24}ON_4$ requires N, 12·61 per cent.).

The above substance was heated with acetic acid for 3 to 4 hours when the colour changed from red to brown. The solid separated, boiled with pyridine and the residue recrystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. above 300°. (Found: C, 90·32; H, 5·01; N, 4·98. $C_{22}H_{15}N$ requires C, 90·10; H, 5·12; N, 4·77 per cent.).

Phenanthraquinonemonoxime di-p-tolylaminoguanidine, obtained by heating the components with alcohol, was crystallised from pyridine in red rectangles, m.p. 227°. (Found: N, 15·42. $C_{29}H_{25}ON_5$ requires N, 15·25 per cent.).

The above compound was heated with acetic acid from 5 to 6 hours when the red colour was changed to deep yellow. The solid was then separated and crystallised from a mixture of water and alcohol in yellow rectangles, m.p. 156°. (Found: C, 87·73; H, 5·05; N, 7·42. $C_{28}H_{20}N_2$ requires C, 87·50; H, 4·94; N, 7·29 per cent.).

2-Nitrophenanthraquinone di-p-tolylaminoguanidine, obtained from alcohol as a brown precipitate, was crystallised from pyridine in brown rectangles, m.p. 228°. (Found: N, 14·55. $C_{29}H_{23}O_3N_5$ requires N, 14·31 per cent.).

The above substance was heated in acetic acid suspension for 4 to 5 hours when the brown colour was changed to bluish-black. This was boiled with acetic acid and pyridine and the residue crystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. above 300°. (Found: C, 78·32; H, 4·23. $C_{22}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires C, 78·10; H, 4·08 per cent.).

2-Nitrophenanthraquinonemonoxime di-p-tolylaminoguanidine, separated from alcohol as a red mass, was crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and water in red rectangles, m.p. 228°. (Found: N, 16·82. $C_{29}H_{24}O_3N_6$ requires N, 16·66 per cent.).

The above substance was heated in acetic acid suspension for 5 to 6 hours and the separated greenish-yellow solid was boiled with pyridine and the residue crystallised from nitrobenzene in rectangles, m.p. 190°. (Found: C, 78·59; H, 4·61. $C_{28}H_{19}O_2N_3$ requires C, 78·32; H, 4·43 per cent.).

2:7-Dinitrophenanthraquinone di-p-tolylaminoguanidine was crystallised from pyridine, m.p. 263°. (Found: N, 15.94. $C_{20}H_{22}O_3N_6$ requires N, 15.73 per cent.).

The above compound was heated for 5 to 6 hours in acetic acid suspension. The separated yellowish-green solid was boiled with pyridine and the residue was crystallised from nitrobenzene in green plates, m.p. above 300°. (Found: C, 68.80; H, 3.53. $C_{22}H_{13}O_4N_3$ requires C, 68.93; H, 3.89 per cent.).

2:7-Dinitrophenanthraquinonemonozime di-p-tolylaminoguanidine which separated from alcohol as a yellow mass could not be crystallised from any solvent, m.p. above 300°. (Found: N, 18.01. $C_{29}H_{23}O_5N_7$ requires N, 17.85 per cent.).

The above compound was heated with acetic acid for 5 to 6 hours when the solid gradually went into solution. On cooling the solution a brown precipitate was obtained which was crystallised from alcohol, in brown rectangles, m.p. 223°. (Found: N, 11.93. $C_{28}H_{18}O_4N_4$ requires N, 11.81 per cent.).

Phenanthraquinone di-β-naphthylaminoguanidine was obtained from the components and alcohol and crystallised from pyridine in golden yellow needles, m.p. 240°. (Found: N, 11.01. $C_{35}H_{24}ON_4$ requires N, 10.85 per cent.).

The above substance was heated in acetic acid suspension for 5 to 6 hours when the yellow colour was changed to grey. The separated solid was boiled with pyridine and crystallised from nitrobenzene as a red powder, m.p. above 300°. (Found: C, 91.44; H, 4.72; N, 4.38. $C_{25}H_{15}N$ requires C, 91.19; H, 4.56; N, 4.25 per cent.).

Phenanthraquinonemonozime di-β-naphthylaminoguanidine, separated from alcohol as a yellow solid and crystallised from pyridine in golden yellow needles, m.p. 235°. (Found: N, 13.43. $C_{35}H_{25}ON_5$ requires N, 13.18 per cent.).

The above substance was heated with acetic acid for 6 to 7 hours. The solid that separated was crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and pyridine in yellow rectangles, m.p. 245°. (Found: C, 89.50; H, 4.86. $C_{35}H_{22}N_2$ requires C, 89.36; H, 4.68 per cent.).

2-Nitrophenanthraquinone di-β-naphthylaminoguanidine that separated from alcohol as a brown mass was crystallised from pyridine and water in brown rectangles, m.p. 200°. (Found: N, 12.69. $C_{35}H_{23}O_3N_5$ requires N, 12.48 per cent.).

The above substance was heated with acetic acid when there was a change of colour from yellow to violet. This was then boiled with pyridine and the residue crystallised from nitrobenzene in violet colour, m.p. 276°. (Found: N, 7.63. $C_{25}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.48 per cent.).

2:7-Dinitrophenanthraquinone di- β -naphthylaminoguanidine was obtained as a brown mass which was crystallised from pyridine in rectangles, m.p. 270°. (Found: N, 13.99. $C_{33}H_{22}O_5N_6$ requires N, 13.66 per cent.).

The above compound was heated for 6 to 7 hours when the colour changed from brown to black. This was then crystallised from nitrobenzene, m.p. above 300°. (Found: C, 71.83; H, 3.35. $C_{25}H_{13}O_4N_3$ requires C, 71.60; H, 3.10 per cent.).

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Received March 12, 1930.